

purified from ethanol. m. p. 189°, Yield 30% (Found : C, 74.13 ; H, 5.56 ; N, 14.23% ; $C_{18}H_{17}N_3O$ requires ; C, 74.22 ; H, 5.84 ; N, 14.43%).

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Chemical and Pharmacological Investigation of *Pogestemon placranthoides*

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THE chemical investigation of *Pogestemon placranthoides*, revealed the presence of straight chain aliphatic hydrocarbon $C_{19}H_{40}$ and three sterols β -sitosterol, stigmasterol and campesterol. The pharmacological screening of the oil obtained from bracts, gave it's LD₅₀ 550 mg/kg. The oil also exhibited significant potentiation of sleeping time induced by hexobarbitone, indicating a CNS depressant activity.

The plant *Pogestemon placranthoides* belongs¹ to family Labiatae and reported to possess² enormous medicinal properties.

The preliminary pharmacological screening of the oil, obtained from pet. ether extract of the plant, gave LD₅₀ value as 550 mg/kg i.p. The CNS depressant activity exhibited by the oil, was further substantiated by the significant potentiation of sleeping time induced by hexobarbitone.

A white low melting (m.p. 32°) aliphatic, straight chain hydrocarbon $C_{19}H_{40}$, was isolated from the oil. The identification of the hydrocarbon, was done with the help of combustion analysis and spectral data.

The chloroform extract of the plant furnished a colourless crystalline solid (m.p. 134-35°), which was identified to be β -sitosterol. The structure of β -sitosterol was ascertained by comparing the spectral data

with that of authentic sample and preparation of derivative.

Though T.L.C. showed β -sitosterol to be homogeneous in nature, mass spectrum revealed it to be a mixture of three compounds, with molecular peaks at 414, 412 and 400. The interpretation of the mass spectrum showed that along with β -sitosterol, other two compounds present were campesterol (M^+ 400) and stigmasterol (M^+ 412).

This is in agreement with the observations made by earlier workers^{3,4} that whenever these sterols co-exist in nature it is extremely difficult to separate them to mass spectral purity.

Analysis of the ash of the plant showed the presence of iron and calcium. The presence of calcium salt may be quite significant in the light of antihemorrhagic properties possessed⁵ by calcium salt and the similar activity exhibited by the plant.

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Search for Possible Anti-Protozoal Compounds in the Quinoxaline Series

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QUINOXALINES having different substitutions are reported to possess wide range of antiprotozoal activity^{1,2}. Investigation on the amebicidal activity of quinoxaline 1,4-(N,N')-dioxides and its substituted compounds³, showed that the compounds were effective in acute amebic dysentery in man although none of them could be used due to toxic side effects. On the other hand many 1-substituted 4 or 5-imidazole derivatives are known to be active against *T. vaginalis*

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and *T. foetus*⁴. Metronidazole, the 1, 2, 5-trisubstituted imidazole derivative possesses high antiamebic as well as antitrichomonal activity⁵. Chloro quinoline is another highly active antiprotozoal compound which has a noveldiamine side chain in its structure⁶.

Taking all these views under consideration quinoxaline derivatives of types (I) and (II) having nitro and/or methyl substituted imidazolyl and 4-diethylamino-1-methyl butylamino side chain have been synthesised to observe their antiprotozoal activity.

2-Hydroxy-3-methyl-5, 8-dimethoxy quinoxaline, prepared by the condensation of 1, 4-dimethoxy-2, 3-diaminobenzene^{7,8} and pyruvic acid, has been chlorinated with POCl₃ to obtain the corresponding 2-chloro quinoxaline derivative which on interaction with the appropriate imidazole or novoldiamine has yielded the desired 2-substituted quinoxaline compounds (I and II).

Pharmacology : None of the compounds described in this paper were found to be significantly active *in vitro* against *E. histolytica*, *T. vaginalis* and *T. foetus* at a concentration of 12.5 mg/ml.

Experimental

2-Hydroxy-3-methyl-5, 8-dimethoxy quinoxaline :

An ice cold solution of pyruvic acid (4.4g), 1, 4-dimethoxy-2, 3-diamino benzene (8.4g) and dry benzene (25 ml.) was boiled in a 250 ml round bottomed flask provided with a Dean and Stark attachment in an oil bath at 120-130° until no more water collected. Finally benzene was distilled off and the residue left in the vessel was leached with aqueous NaHCO₃ (50 ml, 10%) to afford a solid (5.5g) which after washing with water was crystallised in yellow needles from aq. ethanol (yield 50%), m.p. 236-37°; ir (nujol) 3400

(OH, NH), 1670 (amido carbonyl), 1435 (—C—CH_3), 1648 (—C=C— , and —C=N—) cm⁻¹; NMR (CDCl₃) δ 7.9 and 7.7 (1H each, d; phenyl), 4 and 3.9 (3H each, S; OMe), 2.65 (3H, S; CH₃). (Found : C, 59.55; H, 5.15; N, 12.23. C₁₁ H₁₂ O₃ N₂ requires C, 60.00; H, 5.45; N, 12.73%).

2-chloro-3-methyl-5, 8-dimethoxy quinoxaline :

2-Hydroxy - 3-methyl-5, 8-dimethoxy quinoxaline (5.5g) was refluxed with POCl₃ (28 ml) at 120-30° in an oil bath for 1 hr. Excess of POCl₃ was removed under reduced pressure. The residual mass was leached with water and was then extracted with a large volume of ether. On evaporation of ether a yellow solid (1.2g) was obtained. It was crystallised from ethanol in yellow needles; yield 20%; m.p. 174-5°. (Found : C, 54.86; H, 4.29; N, 11.5. C₁₁ H₁₁ N₂O₂Cl requires C, 55.34; H, 4.61; N, 11.74%).

The compounds (I & II) have been synthesised according to the method of Sen and Madan². Method a : A mixture of 2-chloro-3-methyl-5, 8-dimethoxy quinoxaline (.01 mole), imidazole or its derivatives⁹ or 4-diethylamino - 1-methyl - butylamine (.01 mole) and K₂CO₃ (.005 mole) was heated on a boiling water bath for 8 hrs., cooled and filtered. The residual mass left on evaporation was crystallised from a suitable solvent.

DATA ON 2-(1-IMIDAZOLYL)-3-METHYL-5,8-DIMETHOXY QUINOXALINE (I)

Formula	x	y	M.P. °C	Yield %	Analytical					
					Caled %			Found %		
					C	H	N	C	H	N
(i) C ₁₄ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₄ (a)	H	H	112-14 (s)	80	62.22	5.18	20.74	62.31	4.92	20.29
(ii) C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₄ N ₅ (a)	H	NO ₂	107-8 (s)	75	53.33	4.12	22.22	52.9	4.32	21.9
(iii) C ₁₅ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₄ (a)	Me	H	106-7 (s)	70	63.39	5.63	19.71	63.3	5.23	19.25
(iv) C ₁₅ H ₁₅ O ₄ N ₅ (a)	Me	NO ₂	110-12 (s)	70	54.71	4.56	21.27	54.5	4.26	20.85

DATA ON 2-(4-DIETHYLAMINO-1-METHYL BUTYLAMINO)-3-METHYL-5,8-DIMETHOXY QUINOXALINE (II)

Formula	M.P. °C	Yield %	Analytical					
			Caled %			Found %		
			C	H	N	C	H	N
(v) C ₂₀ H ₂₂ O ₂ N ₄ (a) (s)	115-16 (s)	70	66.66	8.88	15.5	66.16	8.39	15.25

a = method used for synthesis.

S = Benzene-Pet. ether (60-80°) mixture (1:1).

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Synthesis of Potential Fungicidal Compounds

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4-THIAZOLIDINONES are well-known for their amoebicidal¹, hypnotic², anticonvulsant³, mosquito-repellent⁴ properties. It has also been shown to have a deep impact on antithyroid activity⁵ with variation in the structure. The presence of N-C-S linkage in the compound has been shown to have antitubercular⁶, antiradiation⁷, nematocidal⁸ and antifungal activity⁹. 2-Aryl-3-dialkylaminoalkyl-4-thiazolidinones were found to be much more active than procaine which showed anaesthetic activity and some 2-aryl-3-alkylaminoalkyl-4-thiazolidinones have shown activity against sciatic nerve block in guinea pigs and spinal anaesthesia in rabbit¹⁰. 2-Aryl-3-alkyl-4-thiazolidinones were found

to be active against psychomotor, anticonvulsant and barbiturate potentiating activity in mice¹¹. Some of the 2- β -naphthylimino-4-thiazolidinones and their aryledene derivatives have been found to be fungicidal against *Alternaria palanduli*¹². 2-Arylimino-3-aryl-4-thiazolidinones and their 1,1-dioxides were found to be effective against *Aspergillus niger*¹³. Bhargawa *et al.* have demonstrated that 2-arylimino-3-aryl-4-thiazolidinones possess considerable fungicidal activity¹⁴⁻¹⁶. Astik *et al.* synthesised 2-methyl-2-(2-hydroxy-5-methylphenyl)-3-aryl-4-thiazolidinones and showed that the introduction of -OH group increases the LD₅₀ in mice¹⁷. In view of the significant biological applicability of 4-thiazolidinones, it was thought desirable to synthesise 2-methyl-2-(2-hydroxy-4, 5-dimethylphenyl)-3-substituted aryl-4-thiazolidinones in order to ascertain effect of substituent in the phenyl nucleus at 3-position of the 4-thiazolidinones on the fungicidal activity against *Helmythosporium appatarnae*, not reported so far.

Experimental

General method of preparation of 2-methyl-2-(2-hydroxy-4, 5-dimethylphenyl)-3-aryl-4-thiazolidinone:

2-Hydroxy-4, 5-dimethyl acetophenone^{18,19} (0.01M), aniline (0.01M) and thioglycolic acid (0.01M) were dissolved in benzene (100 ml) in a round bottomed flask and refluxed with a pinch of ZnCl₂ as a catalyst for 10 hr. Benzene was distilled off. The residue was washed with 2N HCl (10 ml) and then by 10% NaHCO₃ solution (50 ml), except in case of compound Nos. 18, 19, 20 in the Table, washed with water and recrystallised from 95% ethanol. The compounds prepared in 60-70% yield and their physical data are given in the Table.

All the I.R. spectra are taken in nujol mull and showed a sharp absorption peak at 3200-3300 cm⁻¹ indicating the presence of free -OH group. A tertiary amide stretching frequency is also exhibited in the range of 1630-1660 cm⁻¹.

Antifungal screening

Antifungal screening of all 4-thiazolidinones was done by dry weight method. In general, the compounds were found to be inhibitory against *H. appatarnae* at 100 ppm. The parent compound and chloro, methyl, methoxy and nitro substituents in the *o*- and *p*- positions of the phenyl nucleus at 3-position showed relatively greater inhibitory effect as compared to the